

Lethal and sublethal behavioural responses of saline water beetles to acute heat and osmotic stress.

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Title: Lethal and sublethal behavioural responses of saline water beetles to acute heat and osmotic stress.

Running title: Responses of water beetles to stress.

Abstract:

1. As species' physiological breadth determines their potential to deal with environmental changes, and influences individuals' survival and the persistence of populations, information about lethal and sublethal responses could be fundamental for conservation purposes.

2. We used a standard experimental approach to explore mortality and behavioural avoidance responses (i.e. flight and emersion from the water) to a combination of acute heat and osmotic stress on six species of saline water beetles (belonging to *Enochrus*, *Nebrioporus* and *Ochthebius* genera).

3. Heat stress affected survival and behavioural responses in all of the species, whereas osmotic stress and the interaction between both stressors only showed significant effects for the *Ochthebius* genus. Behavioural and survival patterns were highly interrelated across the stress gradients. The *Enochrus* and *Nebrioporus* studied species showed maximum avoidance activity at 35-40°C, and a short (< 30 min) exposure to 45°C was lethal. *Ochthebius* species were the most heat tolerant and displayed increasing behavioural responses with increasing temperature. In the *Nebrioporus* and *Ochthebius* genera, the species occupying lotic, more environmentally stable habitats, showed greater mortality, and avoidance responses were higher or initiated at lower stress thresholds than lentic species. In contrast, both *Enochrus* species displayed a similar mortality, and the lentic species *E. bicolor* emerged and flew more than the lotic *E. falcarius*, in concordance with its higher dispersal capacity.

4. Avoidance responses could provide interesting information about species' physiological amplitudes as a complement to lethal responses. The lotic species here studied showed narrower physiological amplitude (i.e. *N. baeticus* and *O. glaber*) or lower dispersal ability (i.e. *E. falcarius*) than their lentic relatives; both traits could result in a higher vulnerability of lotic species to thermal habitat changes.

Key words: physiological breadth, stress tolerance, behavioural avoidance responses, heat stress, osmotic stress, saline habitats, water beetles, habitat stability, global change.

1 **Introduction**

2 Understanding the ways in which organisms deal with and respond to environmental
3 changes is of considerable importance in determining past and present processes
4 affecting species (Chown, 2001). Species' physiology defines the breadth of
5 fundamental niches (Gaston, 2003) and so, has been identified as relevant when
6 forecasting the effects of the habitat modification on species and population viability
7 (e.g. Tewksbury *et al.*, 2008; Gaston *et al.*, 2009; Helmuth, 2009), particularly in the
8 current context of global warming and stressed biodiversity loss (Deutsch *et al.*, 2008;
9 Bozinovic *et al.*, 2011). Recent studies have shown that laboratory-determined species'
10 physiological amplitudes are a good approximation to species fitness under natural
11 changes in their habitats (Gaston & Spicer, 2001; Deutsch *et al.*, 2008; Barnes *et al.*,
12 2010). As a result, many studies examining the effects of stressors on species'
13 physiology for conservation purposes and predicting future trends under global
14 warming scenarios have emerged (e.g. Swanson *et al.*, 2000; Homan *et al.*, 2003;
15 Pandolfo *et al.*, 2010; Sánchez-Fernández *et al.*, 2010).

16 Together with lethal responses, behavioural adjustments are fundamental in
17 defining species' physiological boundaries and can substantially influence organisms'
18 survival and the persistence of local populations (Huey, 1991; Marais & Chown, 2008;
19 Angilletta, 2009). Organisms employ diverse strategies in order to avoid stress (i.e.
20 avoidance responses), such as moving to other areas through dispersal, or on a smaller
21 scale, to more favourable microclimates within their current habitats (Massot *et al.*,
22 2008; Feder, 2010). These avoidance responses are initiated when organism fitness has
23 deteriorated, and reflect the sublethal stress limits that organisms can tolerate. Despite
24 their informative potential, few studies have included behavioural traits to assess stress

25 tolerance of species (but see Hazell *et al.*, 2010) and as a result, data on the relationship
26 between survival patterns and behavioural avoidance responses under stress are still
27 lacking for many organisms.

28 One of the main environmental stressors for species is temperature, which has
29 long been recognised as one of the most important dimensions of species' niche, since
30 it underpins metabolic activity and life-history processes (Willott & Hassall, 1998),
31 especially for ectotherms (e.g. Bale, 2002; Hoffmann *et al.*, 2003; Chown & Nicolson,
32 2004). Indeed, insect responses to temperature extremes over short periods may be an
33 important driver of population dynamics and, consequently, species' abundance and
34 geographic distribution over longer timescales (Chown & Terblanche, 2007; Hoffmann,
35 2010). In addition to temperature, other stressors can simultaneously affect species and
36 may result in synergistic or even antagonistic effects (Gaston, 2003; Terblanche *et al.*,
37 2011). Salinity has been identified as one of the main factors constraining inland aquatic
38 communities (Williams *et al.*, 1990; Pinder *et al.*, 2005; Rutherford & Kefford, 2005).
39 Recent studies have demonstrated that salinity also affects thermal amplitude of a wide
40 range of organisms, mainly marine (e.g. Kir & Kumlu, 2008; Sardella *et al.*, 2008), but
41 also for inland water bodies taxa (e.g. Sánchez-Fernández *et al.*, 2010). Experimental
42 approaches combining temperature with other environmental stressors (e.g. salinity for
43 aquatic organisms) are highly significant for evaluating the effect of their interactions
44 on organisms' responses, especially in the context of global warming (Pörtner & Farrell,
45 2008; Williams *et al.*, 2008).

46 Here we use a standard experimental approach to explore the physiological
47 tolerance (lethal and sublethal responses) of saline water beetles to heat and osmotic
48 stress, by measuring mortality and two common behavioural avoidance responses

49 displayed by aquatic beetles (i.e. flight and emersion from the water). Locomotion
50 performance is ecologically relevant for insects' survival under extreme environmental
51 stressors (Clusella-Trullas *et al.*, 2010), and flight is the main escape reaction and seems
52 to be promoted by increases in air temperature (Zalom *et al.*, 1980; Velasco & Millán,
53 1998). Emersion from the water is also a typical response that reduces stress and
54 provides support for flight.

55 Species that inhabit inland saline waters are an interesting group to explore
56 stress responses for two main reasons. First, Mediterranean saline water bodies present
57 naturally stressful conditions that comprise high levels of salinity and water
58 temperature. In addition to “natural” stress, climate change predictions forecast
59 increased temperatures and reduced precipitation in the Mediterranean area (IPCC,
60 2007), which, together with an increase in the frequency and severity of extreme events
61 (Easterling *et al.*, 2000), would likely result in intensified heat and salinity stress for
62 organisms that inhabit inland saline waters. Second, saline water fauna offers an ideal
63 group to compare stress responses between related species that occupy habitats with
64 contrasting environmental stability. The climatic variability hypothesis (Janzen, 1967)
65 establishes that climatic stability in the tropics compared to higher latitudes selects for
66 organisms with narrow physiological tolerances amplitudes. At a habitat scale, lentic
67 (standing) water bodies experience greater daily and seasonal temperature and salinity
68 fluctuations than lotic (running) waters (Álvarez-Cobelas *et al.*, 2005; Florencio *et al.*,
69 2009) and so, species in less stable lentic water bodies are forced to develop higher
70 colonisation capacities as well as broader fundamental niches (*sensu* Brown, 1984)
71 compared with their lotic relatives (Ribera, 2008). As a result, the capacity to deal with

72 acute stress and species' sensitivity to environmental changes could be mediated by
73 habitat specialisation.

74 The aim of this study was to compare physiological amplitude through lethal and
75 sublethal behavioural avoidance responses in three pairs of congeneric species of
76 Iberian saline water beetles, with different habitat occupation (lotic-lentic), under acute
77 heat and osmotic stress, as an approximation to their potential to deal with
78 environmental changes in their habitats. It was expected that i) the combination of high
79 temperature and salinity would reduce survival and affect the capacity of water beetles
80 to perform behavioural avoidance responses, ii) patterns of behavioural avoidance
81 responses and mortality would be interrelated across the stress gradient, iii) lotic species
82 would have lower physiological amplitude than lentic (i.e. higher mortality and
83 avoidance activity and/or lower stress thresholds for avoidance responses) and so iv)
84 lotic species would be more susceptible to environmental changes than lentic ones.

85 **Material and methods**

86 *Target species*

87 Coleoptera is one of the most common and richest insect orders in inland saline waters
88 (Millán *et al.*, 2011). The most representative families of water beetles inhabiting saline
89 habitats are Hydraenidae, Hydrophilidae (suborder Polyphaga) and Dytiscidae (suborder
90 Adephaga). The present study focused on three pairs of congeneric beetle species
91 typical of inland meso- and hypersaline systems with contrasting habitat occupation
92 patterns and geographic range size. They are included in three genera: *Nebrioporus* (*N.*
93 *ceresyi* (Aubé, 1836) and *N. baeticus* (Schaum, 1864); family Dytiscidae), *Enochrus* (*E.*
94 *bicolor* (Fabricius, 1792) and *E. falcarius* Hebauer, 1991; family Hydrophilidae) and

95 *Ochthebius* (*O. notabilis* Rosenhauer, 1856 and *O. glaber* Montes & Soler, 1988;
96 family Hydraenidae).

97 *Nebrioporus ceresyi* is a circum-Mediterranean species that occupies standing
98 waters such as wetlands and salt pans, particularly those located in lowland areas near
99 the coast. Conversely, *N. baeticus* is endemic to south eastern Spain, and is found in
100 lotic hypersaline streams usually far from the coast (Fery *et al.*, 1996; Toledo, 2009).

101 *Enochrus bicolor* inhabits lentic saline systems (wetlands and salt pans) and it is
102 found across Europe, northern Africa and Asia east to Mongolia (Schödl, 1998; Hansen,
103 2004). Its related species, *E. falcarius*, has a narrower distribution and occupies saline
104 streams in the southern of Iberian Peninsula, Tunisia and Sicily (Schödl, 1998; Hansen,
105 2004) as well as Morocco (A. Millán *et al.*, pers. obs.) In fact, a recent study has
106 revealed that this species, as currently understood, actually comprises a complex of
107 different lineages, each with restricted, disjointed distributions across the Mediterranean
108 area (Arribas *et al.*, 2012a). Here we studied the Iberian taxon of this species complex
109 ("*E. falcarius* IP" *sensu* Arribas *et al.*, 2012a, here *E. falcarius* for simplicity).

110 *Ochthebius notabilis* is found in saline lagoons across the Iberian Peninsula and
111 northern Africa, whereas *O. glaber* is endemic to the southern Iberian Peninsula and is
112 restricted to running waters (Abellán *et al.*, 2009).

113 ***Experimental design***

114 Survival and behavioural avoidance responses to acute heat and salinity stress were
115 evaluated in the three pairs of sister species selected by employing a static protocol
116 (Lutterschmidt & Hutchison, 1997) which allowed the comparison of specimens'
117 physiological amplitudes between related species to be made.

118 Approximately 400 individuals of each *Enochrus* and *Nebrioporus* species and
119 600 of *Ochthebius* were collected from different areas (one locality per species) in south
120 eastern Spain (see Table 1 for collection locations). Specimens were maintained under
121 laboratory conditions for one week in aquaria with filtered water from the collection
122 sites, artificial aeration and periodic feeding (chironomid larvae for predator species -
123 *Nebrioporus*- *Ruppia maritima* for herbivorous species -*Enochrus*- and biofilm for
124 *Ochthebius*). After this week, the specimens were maintained for 24 h without feeding
125 in an environmental chamber (SANYO MLR-351, Sanyo Electric Co., Ltd., Moriguchi
126 City, Osaka, Japan) at a constant temperature (20°C), 12:12 light:dark cycle and light
127 intensity of 15 $\mu\text{mol.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}$.

128 Finally, ten specimens were randomly assigned to each of the 12 (for *Enochrus*
129 and *Nebrioporus* species) or 20 (for *Ochthebius* species) combined conductivity and
130 temperature treatments, which were replicated three times for each species.
131 Conductivities were chosen according to the environmental gradient where these species
132 appear: 20, 50, 80 mS.cm^{-1} to *Enochrus* and *Nebrioporus* species and 20, 50, 80, 180,
133 240 mS.cm^{-1} to *Ochthebius* species (Velasco *et al.*, 2006). Saline solutions were
134 prepared by dissolving marine salt (Ocean Fish, Prodac®) in distilled water. Tested
135 temperatures represent a gradient from habitual temperatures in the natural habitat of the
136 species (20, 35°C) to extreme temperatures (40, 45°C) that are close to the sublethal and
137 upper lethal limits (UTLs) recorded for these species in previous studies (Sánchez-
138 Fernández *et al.*, 2010; Arribas *et al.*, 2012a,b). The inland saline water bodies of the
139 Iberian Peninsula that the studied species inhabit are characterised by extreme and large
140 seasonal and daily variations in environmental conditions (Velasco *et al.*, 2006; Millán
141 *et al.* 2011; Gutiérrez-Cánovas *et al.*, 2012). For example, in the Rambla Salada stream

142 (SE Spain), the observed daily water temperature amplitude could commonly reach 10-
143 12°C and up to 18°C, and water temperatures of 35°C and heating rates of
144 approximately 1°C/2h are frequent during the summer (J. Velasco, unpublished data).

145 Each experimental aquarium contained 100 ml of solution and an artificial stone
146 partially emerged to help individuals emerge and fly to avoid stressful conditions.
147 Aquaria were introduced in a temperature-controlled water bath (Precistern 6000141,
148 J.P Selecta, Barcelona, Spain) (i.e. $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). Each set of individuals was removed from the
149 acclimation aquaria and immediately exposed to the assigned treatment for 30 min.
150 During this exposure period, behavioural responses and mortality were recorded. The
151 number of individuals on the stone in each aquarium was recorded every two minutes in
152 order to determine emersion response. Specimens that flew or were dead at each two
153 minutes interval were counted and removed. However, due to the small size of
154 individuals from the *Ochthebius* species, it was impossible to determine the exact time
155 of the specimens' death, and total mortality was recorded at the end of the experiment
156 for *O. glaber* and *O. notabilis*.

157 Mortality was expressed as the percentage of individuals that died during 30
158 minutes of acute exposure. For behavioural responses, in the case of *Enochrus* and
159 *Nebrioporus* species, percentage of emersions and flights in each treatment was
160 expressed in relation to the number of alive individuals that were present in the aquaria
161 at the moment of recording (i.e. each two minutes). For *Ochthebius* species, since
162 dynamic mortality data were not available, behavioural responses were expressed as the
163 mean percentage of individuals that emerged or flew (respectively) during the
164 experimental time divided by the number of surviving individuals after exposure.

165 ***Data analysis***

166 Multifactorial MANOVA analyses were performed using the Pillai's trace test to assess
167 the global effect of temperature, conductivity and species on overall response variables
168 within each genus. Univariate analyses of variance (ANOVAs) were also conducted to
169 determine the effects of each factor and interactions independently on each variable.
170 Mortality percentages were arcsine transformed before the analyses.

171 Because homocedasticity and normality of raw data and GLM residuals were not
172 satisfied in some cases, a more conservative approach was employed by reducing the
173 significance level ($p \leq 0.01$) and using post-hoc analyses with Bonferroni correction to
174 identify significant differences amongst treatments (Underwood, 1997; Rutherford,
175 2001). All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS for Windows, Rel. 15.0.1.
176 2006. Chicago: SPSS Inc.

177 **3. Results**

178 *Effects of temperature and conductivity on response variables*

179 Multivariate tests showed global significant differences in response variables between
180 temperature levels in all pairs of species examined (Table 2). Similar results were found
181 in the ANOVAs of each response variable (see Table 3 for mortality, Table 4 for
182 emersion and Table 5 for flight). In general, both behavioural responses and mortality
183 increased with increasing temperatures, although in *Enochrus* and *Nebrioporus* species
184 the most extreme temperature significantly increased mortality and reduced behavioural
185 responses.

186 The effect of conductivity was only significant for the *Ochthebius* species (Table
187 2) for all of the response variables (Tables 3, 4 and 5). The interaction of temperature x
188 conductivity also showed significant effects for these species (Table 2) and the response

189 patterns across heat and osmotic stress differed between the two congeneric species (see
190 below).

191 ***Lethal responses: Mortality***

192 Both *Enochrus* species showed similar tolerance to acute heat stress (see Species and
193 Temperature x Species interaction in Table 3). *Enochrus bicolor* and *E. falcarius*
194 displayed high survival at all temperature levels tested, except at 45 °C, where after 30
195 minutes of exposure most individuals died (Fig. 1a).

196 Similarly, for both *Nebrioporus* species the increased temperature reduced the
197 specimens' survival, and most individuals died at 45°C (Fig. 1b). Total mortality of the
198 lotic species *N. baeticus* was significantly higher than for the lentic *N. ceresyi* (Species
199 in Table 3), and this difference was especially great at 40°C ($P < 0.001$ in post hoc test
200 for species difference at 40 °C; Fig. 1b).

201 *Ochthebius* species displayed varying tolerances to both stressors (Temperature
202 x Conductivity x Species in Table 3). Mortality of the lotic species *O. glaber* was higher
203 than in the lentic *O. notabilis* in all of the stress treatments (Species in Table 3, Fig.
204 1c,d). In *O. glaber*, mortality increased progressively with temperature. At the higher
205 temperatures (40-45°C), the mortality of *O. glaber* was also significantly greater at the
206 most extreme conductivity level (240 mS.cm⁻¹) (Fig. 1c). However, in *O. notabilis*,
207 mortality was low or null at 20, 35 and 40°C; only 45°C significantly reduced survival
208 and no significant differences in mortality were observed among conductivity levels
209 (see Conductivity post hoc tests for each species in Fig. 1c,d).

210 ***Sublethal behavioural responses***

211 ***Emersion***

212 The lentic species *E. bicolor* emerged more than the lotic *E. falcarius* (see Species in
213 Table 4). However, *Enochrus* species showed no significant differences in emersion
214 activity pattern across temperature treatments (Temperature x Species in Table 4), i.e.
215 emersion increased from 20 to 40°C, when the maximum emersion response was
216 reached by both species (Fig. 2a).

217 No significant differences either in emersion response magnitude or patterns
218 across temperature treatments were found between lotic and lentic *Nebrioporus* species
219 (Species and Temperature x Species in Table 4). Thus, 40°C was the critical thermal
220 threshold where maximum emersion activity was observed for both species, after which
221 no further emersion was recorded (Fig. 2b).

222 Similarly, no significant differences in magnitude of emersion response were
223 detected between the *Ochthebius* species (Species in Table 4) and a similar response
224 pattern across temperature and conductivity treatments was displayed by both species
225 (Temperature x Conductivity x Species in Table 4). The number of emersions increased
226 with increasing temperature, reaching the maximum response at 45°C (Fig. 2c,d), and
227 decreased significantly at high conductivities. The combination of the highest
228 temperatures (40-45°C) and conductivity (240 mS.cm⁻¹) caused a significant reduction
229 in emersion response (Conductivity x Temperature in Table 4, Fig. 2c,d).

230 **Flight**

231 Between *Enochrus* species, the lentic *E. bicolor* showed a higher flight response than
232 the lotic *E. falcarius* (see Species in Table 5, Fig. 3a) but flight activity patterns were
233 similar between both species and across all the temperature range (Temperature and
234 Species x Temperature in Table 5, Fig. 3a).

235 In *Nebrioporus* species, the lotic *N. baeticus* flew more than the lentic *N. ceresyi*
236 at all temperature levels (Species in Table 5). The response pattern did not significantly
237 differ between both species; the highest flight activity was displayed at 35°- 40°C and
238 minimum response was shown at 20 and 45°C (Temperature and Species x Temperature
239 in Table 5, Fig. 3b).

240 Flight response had a similar magnitude between both *Ochthebius* species
241 (Species in Table 5). However, response patterns across temperature and conductivity
242 treatments differed between the lotic and the lentic species (Temperature x Conductivity
243 x Species in Table 5). Flight activity increased with increasing heat stress in both
244 species but *O. glaber* reached the maximum response at 45°C and *O. notabilis* at 40°C
245 (Fig 3c,d). The effect of conductivity on flight was only significant for the lentic species
246 *O. notabilis*, which showed the greatest flight activity at the higher conductivities (180
247 and 240 mS.cm⁻¹) (see Conductivity post hoc tests for each species in Fig. 3c,d). The
248 temperature x conductivity interaction differed between species (Table 5). At the most
249 extreme temperatures (40-45°C), the lotic species *O. glaber* showed a significant
250 decrease in flight response at 240 mS.cm⁻¹ (Fig. 3c). In contrast, at the highest
251 temperatures (40 and 45°C) the lentic *O. notabilis* showed the maximum flight response
252 at the highest conductivities (180 and 240 mS.cm⁻¹) (Fig. 3c,d).

253 Discussion

254 *Does the combination of high temperature and salinity stress affect lethal and sublethal*
255 *responses in saline water beetles?*

256 In our acute stress experiments, a reduced effect of salinity and its interaction with
257 temperature on survival and behavioural avoidance responses was observed. Only for

258 the *Ochthebius* species, the combination of high conductivities and extreme
259 temperatures had a synergistic effect, reducing emersion response of both species, and
260 also reducing flight activity and specimens' survival of the less tolerant species *O.*
261 *glaber*. In this case, the interactions between both factors appeared to be more important
262 near the tolerance limits, as other authors have stated in regards to a coral species (Coles
263 & Jokiel, 1978). Osmoregulatory mechanisms could be impaired at extreme
264 temperatures, which could explain the severe fitness loss observed in the individuals of
265 *O. glaber* exposed to high temperatures and salinities.

266 An acute exposure to osmotic stress did not affect survival or behavioural
267 responses on the *Nebrioporus* and *Enochrus* species studied here. However, recent work
268 has documented the effect of chronic exposure to salinity on the lethal thermal limits for
269 *N. baeticus*, *N. ceresyi* (Sánchez-Fernández *et al.*, 2010) and *E. falcarius* (Arribas *et al.*,
270 2012a); the upper thermal limits of these species are higher in individuals acclimated to
271 relatively high salinities and temperatures. Thus, the effect of salinity and the interaction
272 of temperature x salinity on these species might be highly mediated by exposure time, in
273 agreement with many studies that have found that lethal and sublethal responses could
274 differ depending on the duration of exposure to a determined stressor (e.g Reynaldi &
275 Liess, 2005; Terblanche *et al.*, 2008; Nel *et al.*, 2011). In general, the physiology and
276 behavioural regulation ability of the studied saline species was affected more
277 immediately and strongly by the heat shock than the acute osmotic stress. To date,
278 similar studies evaluating the effect of acute exposure to temperature and salinity on
279 aquatic organisms' survival and sublethal responses are scarce, so it is difficult to
280 discern if the pattern found in these species is common.

281 *Are species' behavioural and lethal responses interrelated?*

282 As a general pattern in all of the studied species, avoidance responses increased in
283 magnitude as stress levels intensified, within a range of low to moderate heat and
284 salinity stress below their tolerance limits. However, when stress levels approached to
285 these limits, behavioural thermoregulation was impaired possibly owing to the failure of
286 physiological mechanisms regulating temperature and salinity tolerance.

287 In *Enochrus* and *Nebrioporus* species, low mortality and increasing emersion
288 and flight activity were recorded between 20 and 40°C. At 45°C only a few individuals
289 survived, and behavioural responses were significantly reduced due to the irreversible
290 physiological damage caused by the extreme heat stress.

291 *Ochthebius* species were the most heat tolerant and in general displayed more
292 intense behavioural activity. The higher tolerance to temperature observed in these
293 species is congruent with the extreme hypersaline habitats they inhabit (Velasco *et al.*,
294 2006; Abellán *et al.*, 2009; Millán *et al.*, 2011). Osmoregulation mechanisms could
295 enhance their thermal resistance through the accumulation of osmolytes in the
296 haemolymph, and the consequent reduction of protein denaturation during heat stress
297 (Harada *et al.*, 2011), which would provide these species a cross-tolerance to salinity
298 and heat. This cross-tolerance between different stressors has been studied in some
299 terrestrial insects (e.g. Tauber *et al.*, 1986, Bayley *et al.*, 2001; Bublily *et al.*, 2012).
300 However, there have been no studies on the mechanism of such cross-tolerance in saline
301 species.

302 The ability to develop behavioural responses is highly determined by
303 individual's physiological tolerance (Wijnhoven *et al.*, 2002), a pattern which has been
304 observed in our results. Furthermore, behavioural adjustments modify the
305 environmental conditions that an organism experiences, and therefore influence its

306 fitness and short-term physiological performance (Huey, 1991). Consequently, a proper
307 evaluation of the physiological amplitudes of species should include not only measures
308 of survival limits, but also other sublethal responses.

309 *Are the lotic species more sensitive to stress than lentic species?*

310 As expected, in two of the three studied species pairs (i.e. *Nebrioporus* and *Ochthebius*
311 species), those occupying lotic, more environmentally stable habitats, were more
312 sensitive to heat stress.

313 Within the *Nebrioporus* species, the lotic *N. baeticus* was less tolerant to heat
314 stress than the lentic *N. ceresyi*. This result is in concordance with data obtained from
315 lethal thermal limits experiments by Sánchez-Fernández *et al.* (2010), where *N. ceresyi*
316 showed greater thermal range than *N. baeticus*. Both species displayed maximum
317 behavioural responses at the same temperature thresholds (35-40°C), although *N.*
318 *baeticus*, the less tolerant species, showed higher flight activity than *N. ceresyi*.

319 Parallel differences in stress responses were found within the *Ochthebius*
320 species. *Ochthebius glaber*, which inhabits lotic water bodies, showed greater mortality
321 and initiated avoidance responses at lower stress thresholds than *O. notabilis*, which
322 occupies lentic habitats with greater thermal and saline variability (Abellán *et al.*, 2007;
323 2009). At the most extreme heat level, *O. glaber* flew more than *O. notabilis* in lower
324 salinities, while at the most extreme conductivity (240 ms.cm⁻¹) *O. notabilis* showed
325 more flight and emersion activity in concordance with its greater salinity and heat
326 tolerance.

327 Contrary to the pattern observed in the *Nebrioporus* and *Ochthebius* species,
328 both *Enochrus* species displayed similar tolerance to heat stress. However, *E. bicolor*,

329 the lentic species, exhibited higher emersion and flight activity than *E. falcarius*. These
330 results are in agreement with those obtained by Arribas *et al.* (2012a), where dispersal
331 capacity, rather than physiological tolerances, was identified as driving biogeographical
332 differences between lentic and lotic species in the *E. bicolor* group (including *E. bicolor*
333 and *E. falcarius*).

334 Our results suggest that tolerance to environmental changes in the studied
335 species could be mediated by habitat stability. Differences in the environmental stability
336 of lentic and lotic habitats could promote the evolution of different stress response
337 strategies among species inhabiting each habitat (Ribera, 2008). Thus, species adapted
338 to less stable lentic habitats would have developed higher colonisation capabilities that
339 would be mediated by both improved physiological tolerances (e.g. *Nebrioporus* and
340 *Octhebius* species) or dispersal abilities (e.g. *Enochrus* species) compared to their lotic
341 counterparts.

342 *Which species within each genus could be more susceptible to climate change on the*
343 *basis of these lethal and behavioural responses?*

344 Despite the wide tolerance of saline species to environmental changes (Millán *et al.*,
345 2011), on the basis of the responses studied here, the lotic species *N. baeticus* and *O.*
346 *glaber* could be more vulnerable than their respective lentic species *N. ceresyi* and *O.*
347 *notabilis* to a rapid temperature increase. Particularly, *O. glaber*, which is considered to
348 be highly threatened in the Iberian Peninsula (Sánchez-Fernández *et al.*, 2008), seems to
349 be the most endangered due to its higher sensitivity to heat and osmotic stress coupled
350 with the high fragmentation of its habitats (hypersaline streams) and low dispersal
351 capacity (Abellán *et al.*, 2007; 2009; Arribas *et al.*, 2012b). In the case of *Enochrus*

352 species, the lower dispersal ability of *E. falcarius* (Arribas *et al.*, 2012a) also points to a
353 higher vulnerability to environmental changes than for the lentic *E. bicolor*.

354 However, even in a context of rapid environmental changes, variation rates in
355 natural conditions are much slower than those tested here, allowing organisms to
356 acclimate through short-term plasticity (Stillman, 2003). Thus, despite the study of
357 physiological amplitudes provides valuable information about potential species'
358 sensitivity to environmental changes, species' responses in nature could be also affected
359 by phenotypic plasticity, which could enhance survival rates. Although in unpredictable
360 environments such as saline water bodies, acclimation effects would be reduced (Chown
361 & Terblanche, 2007), further studies applying dynamic protocols with more gradual
362 change rates could be key to obtain more realistic estimates of species responses to
363 increasing environmental stress.

364 In summary, data from this study suggest that specialised aquatic fauna in saline
365 lotic habitats could represent a vulnerable component of arid environments' biodiversity
366 (Millán *et al.*, 2011). We therefore propose that biomonitoring and extra conservation
367 efforts be focussed on these singular habitats.

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379 Data analysis and discussion: P.A., V.C., A.M., J.V. and S.P.

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569

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570 **Figure legends**

571 **Figure 1.** Mean \pm SE mortality of each species. Significant differences determined
572 by post-hoc analysis employing Bonferroni correction are indicated as follows: by
573 capital letters in the legend for conductivity levels, by lower case above the bars for
574 temperature levels, by numbers above the bars for conductivity levels within the
575 same temperature level and by asterisks above the bars for differences between
576 species within the same treatment.

577 **Figure 2.** Mean \pm SE emersion of each species. Significant differences determined
578 by post-hoc analysis employing Bonferroni correction are indicated as follows: by
579 capital letters in the legend for conductivity levels, by lower case above the bars for
580 temperature levels, by numbers above the bars for conductivity levels within the
581 same temperature level and by asterisks above the bars for differences between
582 species within the same treatment.

583 **Figure 3.** Mean \pm SE total flight of each species. Significant differences determined
584 by post-hoc analysis employing Bonferroni correction are indicated as follows: by
585 capital letters in the legend for conductivity levels, by lower case above the bars for
586 temperature levels, by numbers above the bars for conductivity levels within the
587 same temperature level and by asterisks above the bars for differences between
588 species within the same treatment.

589

590 **Tables**

591 **Table 1.** Species' natural habitat information and collection sites data (geographical
 592 coordinates and mean conductivity)

<i>Species</i>	<i>Habitat occupancy</i>	<i>Conductivity range (mS.cm⁻¹)</i>	<i>Sample location</i>	<i>Latitude</i>	<i>Longitude</i>	<i>Mean conductivity of the locality (mS.cm⁻¹)</i>
<i>N. ceresyi</i>	Lentic	2 - 128	Laguna Cotorrillo, Murcia	37.82516	-0.76196	60
<i>N. baeticus</i>	Lotic	2 - 160	Río Chicamo, Murcia	38.21753	-1.05113	19
<i>E. bicolor</i>	Lentic	4 - 103	Laguna del Mojón Blanco, Albacete	38.47530	-1.25582	65
<i>E. falcarius</i>	Lotic	7 - 160	Rambla Salada, Murcia	38.16993	-1.12565	70
<i>O. notabilis</i>	Lentic	50 - 220	Estrecho de la Salineta, Alicante	38.43459	-0.78006	140
<i>O. glaber</i>	Lotic	20 - 250	Rambla de Librilla, Murcia	37.90656	-1.37102	180

593

594 **Table 2.** Effect of temperature and conductivity on overall response variables for
 595 *Enochrus*, *Nebrioporus* and *Ochthebius* species.

Effect	Pillai's trace	F	d.f	P - value
<i>Enochrus</i>				
Temperature	1.597	18.223	9	< 0.001
Conductivity	0.065	0.523	6	0.789
Species	0.361	8.654	3	< 0.001
Temperature x Conductivity	0.312	0.929	18	0.545
Temperature x Species	0.377	2.302	9	0.019
Conductivity x Species	0.182	1.572	6	0.164
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	0.321	0.957	18	0.512
<i>Nebrioporus</i>				
Temperature	1.909	27.981	9	< 0.001
Conductivity	0.042	0.335	6	0.917
Species	0.406	10.460	3	< 0.001
Temperature x Conductivity	0.199	0.568	18	0.918
Temperature x Species	0.622	4.185	9	< 0.001
Conductivity x Species	0.008	0.060	6	0.999
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	0.236	0.683	18	0.079
<i>Ochthebius</i>				
Temperature	1.100	15.442	9	< 0.001
Conductivity	0.815	7.460	12	< 0.001
Species	0.524	28.637	3	< 0.001
Temperature x Conductivity	0.895	2.835	36	< 0.001
Temperature x Species	0.604	6.718	9	< 0.001
Conductivity x Species	0.527	4.259	12	< 0.001
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	0.796	2.408	36	< 0.001

596 d.f., degrees of freedom

597
 598
 599
 600
 601

602 **Table 3.** Effect of temperature and conductivity on mortality for *Enochrus*,
 603 *Nebrioporus* and *Ochthebius* species.

Dependent variable: Mortality				
Effect	SS	d.f.	F	<i>P</i> - value
<i>Enochrus</i>				
Full model	18.487	23	40.640	< 0.001
Intercept	7.482	1	378.316	< 0.001
Temperature	18.172	3	306.265	< 0.001
Conductivity	0.049	2	1.236	0.300
Species	0.000	1	0.019	0.891
Temperature x Conductivity	0.183	6	1.539	0.186
Temperature x Species	0.023	3	0.389	0.761
Conductivity x Species	0.014	2	0.350	0.706
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	0.046	6	0.387	0.884
Error	0.949	48		
<i>Nebrioporus</i>				
Full model	32189.498	23	15.393	< 0.001
Intercept	20.518	1	1188.512	< 0.001
Temperature	28.149	3	543.505	< 0.001
Conductivity	0.020	2	0.577	0.565
Species	0.198	1	11.460	0.001
Temperature x Conductivity	0.013	6	0.122	0.993
Temperature x Species	0.807	3	15.577	< 0.001
Conductivity x Species	0.000	2	0.007	0.993
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	0.108	6	1.047	0.408
Error	0.829	48		
<i>Ochthebius</i>				
Full model	15.435	39	24.074	< 0.001
Intercept	9.886	1	601.357	< 0.001
Temperature	9.913	3	201.007	< 0.001
Conductivity	0.853	4	12.965	< 0.001
Species	1.386	1	84.340	< 0.001
Temperature x Conductivity	0.874	12	4.432	< 0.001
Temperature x Species	1.084	3	21.982	< 0.001
Conductivity x Species	0.466	4	7.082	< 0.001
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	0.858	12	4.351	< 0.001
Error	1.315	80		

604 SS, sum of squares; d.f., degrees of freedom

605

606 **Table 4.** Effect of temperature and conductivity on emersion response for
 607 *Enochrus*, *Nebrioporus* and *Ochthebius* species.

Dependent variable: Emersion				
Effect	SS	d.f.	F	P - value
<i>Enochrus</i>				
Full model	37775.999	23	4.504	< 0.001
Intercept	104761.476	1	287.253	< 0.001
Temperature	30534.568	3	27.908	< 0.001
Conductivity	313.644	2	0.430	0.653
Species	2702.195	1	7.409	0.009
Temperature x Conductivity	810.362	6	0.370	0.894
Temperature x Species	2429.023	3	2.220	0.098
Conductivity x Species	809.732	2	1.110	0.338
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	176.76	6	0.081	0.998
Error	17505.627	48		
<i>Nebrioporus</i>				
Full model	32189.498	23	15.393	< 0.001
Intercept	21606.420	1	237.638	< 0.001
Temperature	31030.047	3	113.761	< 0.001
Conductivity	63.235	2	0.348	0.708
Species	108.586	1	1.194	0.280
Temperature x Conductivity	456.951	6	0.838	0.547
Temperature x Species	497.775	3	1.825	0.155
Conductivity x Species	2.028	2	0.011	0.989
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	30.876	6	0.057	0.999
Error	4364.243	48		
<i>Ochthebius</i>				
Full model	51983.679	39	6.748	< 0.001
Intercept	67635.235	1	342.389	< 0.001
Temperature	32140.818	3	54.235	< 0.001
Conductivity	6787.594	4	8.590	< 0.001
Species	1306.765	1	6.615	0.012
Temperature x Conductivity	7640.230	12	3.223	0.001
Temperature x Species	348.966	3	0.589	0.624
Conductivity x Species	1171.376	4	1.482	0.215
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	2587.929	12	1.092	0.379
Error	15803.137	80		

608
609

SS, sum of squares; d.f., degrees of freedom

610 **Table 5.** Effect of temperature and conductivity on flight response for *Enochrus*,
 611 *Nebrioporus* and *Ochthebius* species.

Dependent variable: Flight				
Effect	SS	d.f.	F	P - value
<i>Enochrus</i>				
Full model	138.181	23	1.1774	0.047
Intercept	192.263	1	56.765	< 0.001
Temperature	32.743	3	3.222	0.031
Conductivity	2.596	2	0.383	0.684
Species	26.957	1	7.962	0.007
Temperature x Conductivity	8.524	6	0.419	0.862
Temperature x Species	23.795	3	2.342	0.085
Conductivity x Species	7.509	2	1.109	0.338
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	36.047	6	1.774	0.125
Error	162.576	48		
<i>Nebrioporus</i>				
Full model	194.797	23	2.293	0.008
Intercept	110.767	1	29.986	< 0.001
Temperature	63.057	3	5.690	0.002
Conductivity	1.014	2	0.137	0.872
Species	49.030	1	13.273	0.001
Temperature x Conductivity	22.756	6	1.027	0.420
Temperature x Species	29.103	3	2.626	0.061
Conductivity x Species	1.257	2	0.170	0.844
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	28.579	6	1.289	0.280
Error	177.311	48		
<i>Ochthebius</i>				
Full model	224.753	39	4.228	< 0.001
Intercept	377.240	1	276.754	< 0.001
Temperature	73.485	3	17.970	< 0.001
Conductivity	20.944	4	3.841	0.007
Species	0.147	1	0.108	0.744
Temperature x Conductivity	35.477	12	2.169	0.021
Temperature x Species	19.307	3	4.721	0.004
Conductivity x Species	30.157	4	5.531	0.001
Temperature x Conductivity x Species	45.236	12	2.766	0.003
Error	711.040	80		

612 SS, sum of squares; d.f., degrees of freedom

613

614 **Figures**

615 **Fig. 1**

616

617 Fig. 2

618

619 Fig. 3

